

Checklist: Minimum Criteria for the Reuse of Research Data

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1. Preliminary Remarks

1.1 Purpose of the Checklist

This checklist serves as a guide when initiating a project that uses existing research data, such as survey results, statistics, measured values, or image and video data from other studies. This may be the case for a scientific paper or a student assignment, for example. The checklist is aimed at both supervisors and individuals who directly reuse data. It includes general steps, the minimum criteria to be fulfilled, and additional information.

1.2 Initial Scenarios for Data Reuse

There are essentially two scenarios for the reuse of existing research data:

- *Scenario A - From the research question to the data:* Initially, a research question is formulated, at least in general terms. It is then determined which data is needed to answer this question.
- *Scenario B - From data to the research question:* Based on existing data sets, it is determined which research question can be answered using this data.

In practice, these two scenarios are often not clearly distinguishable. Elements from both approaches are frequently combined. For example, a research question might be defined first and then adapted or even reformulated based on the data available.

1.3 Possible Data Sources and Search Strategies

Both published and unpublished data are suitable for reuse. There are various options for searching for **data published online**. The following overview of potential search strategies serves as a guide:

- *Search Repositories:* There are three types of repositories to distinguish:
 - Generic Repositories (z.B. [Zenodo](https://zenodo.org/), [Dryad](https://www.dryad.org/)),
 - Discipline-specific Repositories (z.B. [Ag Data Commons](https://www.ag-data.com/), [DaSCH](https://www.dasch.org/))
 - Institutional Repositories (z.B. [ETH Research Collection](https://www.ethz.ch/research-collection), [BORIS portal](https://www.boris.unz.ch/)).

Repositories typically contain data collected in an academic context. Relevant repositories can be found through the [re3data](https://re3data.org/) directory.

- *Use Specialised Search Engines:* Platforms such as [Google Dataset Search](https://www.google.com/datasetsearch/) or [BASE](https://www.base-search.net/) do not have their own database. They refer to the offerings of various repositories. This enables a parallel search in several repositories.

- *Literature Research*: In many scientific publications, you will find links or references to the datasets on which the respective publication is based.
- *Consult Authorities and Organizations*: Relevant authorities and organizations that collect statistical data (e.g., [the Federal Statistical Office](#), [the Federal Food Safety and Veterinary Office](#), or [Reporters Without Borders](#)) can also be helpful sources.
- *Use Community-operated Platforms*: On platforms such as [Kaggle](#) or [GitHub](#), data scientists and IT developers provide data and code.

Unpublished data can, for example, originate from the following sources:

- Own (Completed) Research Projects
- (Research) Collaborations: (e.g., data provided by project partners such as a hospital or an industry partner)
- (Research) Contacts: (e.g., research colleagues at the institute or university)

2. Checklist

A project for the reuse of existing research data generally begins with two steps: data research and quality check (see sections 2.1 and 2.2). The first step involves searching for the required data (see section 1.3). After a successful data search, the second step is to check whether the dataset found is fundamentally suitable for reuse. This is merely an initial assessment. Whether the data is suitable for analysis as part of the planned project can only be determined with certainty in the course of the project. These two steps—the data research and the quality check—are listed in the following checklist. It sets out the minimum criteria to be fulfilled as well as further information.

2.1 Data Research

Required data is available	<input type="checkbox"/>
<p>The reuse of existing datasets is more sensible and expedient than collecting your own data as part of the planned project.</p> <p><i>Note: This is the case, for example, if the test conditions are not reproducible, the data collection requires considerable time resources, or the aim is to provide students with knowledge about data reuse.</i></p>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<p>Answering the research question based on the available data makes an original scientific contribution.</p> <p><i>Note: For student work or other studies that do not aim to make an innovative research contribution (e.g., replication studies), fulfilling this criterion is optional.</i></p>	<input type="checkbox"/> <i>optional</i>

2.2 Quality Assessment

Content Aspects: The available information is sufficient and credible regarding the interpretability of the data.

The available documentation is sufficient to understand and interpret the data.

Note: Data is generally not self-explanatory. To understand it, additional information is required, such as details on the methods and instruments used to collect the data or notes on the variables. This information can be documented in metadata or separate files (e.g., README or codebook). If documentation is missing or insufficient, it is advisable to contact the data authors for further clarification.

The data was processed and aggregated only to the extent necessary for it to be interpreted according to the requirements of the planned project.

Note: To answer the relevant research question, access to the raw data is often necessary. Information in the processed data sets (e.g., due to the anonymisation of the raw data) is often insufficient. In such cases, it is advisable to contact the data authors and request access to the raw or less aggregated data.

The credibility and reliability of the data are ensured.

Note: When reusing data, it is essential to ensure that they are credible and reliable. This is necessary to guarantee the quality and trustworthiness of the scientific results based on them. The credibility of the data cannot always be determined upon initial inspection. However, there are some indications that may cast doubt on the reliability of the data. Examples include a questionable reputation of the data source, suspicion of unauthorised data manipulation (e.g., due to nearly perfect or unusual data patterns, unfounded changes in test conditions, extremely high or low values), and lack of transparency or documentation of data collection.

<p>Technical aspects: The technical reusability of the data is guaranteed.</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<p>The software for opening and editing the data is available or can be licensed.</p> <p><i>Note: The use of some software programs requires the purchase of a license. Universities often purchase licenses for proprietary software so that their members can use these programs free of charge. However, there are often open-source alternatives to such proprietary software that are available free of charge, such as PSPP instead of SPSS and GIMP instead of Adobe Photoshop.</i></p>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<p>Specialised knowledge is required to operate this software.</p> <p><i>Note: Students, for example, often lack specialised software knowledge. Therefore, the supervisors often have to carry out preliminary work by preparing the data set for further analysis themselves. This is often very time-consuming.</i></p>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<p>The necessary infrastructure for data storage and processing is available for the planned project.</p> <p><i>Note: In some cases, the amount of data can be large, requiring high computing power. In such instances, it is advisable to contact the relevant service centres within your institution (e.g., ICT) or the specialist community for support.</i></p>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<p>Legal Aspects: Reuse is permitted.</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<p>It is explicitly stated under what conditions the data may be reused.</p> <p><i>Note: For published data, the terms of use can be found, for example, in the licensing agreements, the legal notice, or the 'Terms & Conditions' on the websites of the data providers. For unpublished data, the reuse conditions are often specified in various agreements (e.g., informed consent or contracts with industry partners). In case of uncertainties, it is advisable to contact the legal service of your institution or the data authors.</i></p>	<input type="checkbox"/>